

GENGHIS KHAN'S ADVANCE TO THE STATE OF KHORAZMSHAH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205399>

After capturing the main parts of Movarounnahr – Sirdarya basin, Zarafshan, Kashkadarya valleys, Bukhara oasis, Shosh and Fergana valleys, Genghis Khan now turned his main attention to the Khorezm region, the center of the Khorezmshah state. He put his sons Jo'chi, Chigatoy, Oktoy (Ugedey) in charge of this campaign. In particular, the khan attached great importance to the conquest of ancient Urganch (Gurganj), the largest city of the Muslim East, where culture and trade flourished.

As mentioned above, the second important issue that Genghis Khan set before himself was the capture of the capital of the Khoramzshah state. In this regard, Genghis Khan sent his representative Donishmand Hajib to the Turkon Khatun who was staying in the capital. In the letter brought by the representative, Genghis Khan demanded that he submit to him, considering himself to be the defender of Turkon Khotun's interests. In exchange, Turkon Khatuna was given lands on the south side of Khorezm, Khorasan, and Amudarya. Gurganj has a strong defensive wall, it even withstood the siege of Shahabeddin al-Guri, the Ghurian sultan in 1204. The people of the capital city were distinguished by their courage and military training. The wise Hajib "Malikai Olam" Turkon told Khatun that his son Sultan Muhammad had already fled, and that many regions of the country had already passed into the hands of the Mongols.

Naturally, these news broke the strength and courage of the Turkon wife. He collected all the valuables and started to leave the capital quickly. While leaving the capital, he committed another evil. The princess ordered to drown the governors of different countries, cities, regions, their sons, a total of 26 people, who were held hostage, were once captured, in the Amudarya. This strange behavior of Turkon's wife caused many people to become even more disappointed with her. The Turkan wife went to the Ilol fortress in Mozondaran and hid with her relatives and wealth. The fort was very strong, food supply, weapons were sufficient. The Mongols besieged the fortress for four months.

Tired of the siege and the lack of water, the Turkoman Khatun eventually surrendered. The Mongols killed the young sons of the sultan, and the women were distributed to Genghis Khan's relatives.

The Turkon wife had a miserable life as a slave to Genghis Khan's women in captivity. He died in poverty in Karakorum in 1233. At the beginning of 1221, Jalaluddin, who was proclaimed "sultan", and the princes Akshah and Uzlagshahs came to Gurganj. But the political situation in Gurganj, the assassination of Qutlugh Khan, the former viceroy of Jand, and the treacherous behavior of the Kipchak generals, did not want Jaloliddin to lead the defense of the city. In such a situation, it became clear that it was impossible to organize a defense. After these events, Jalaluddin together with Temur Malik left the city with 300 people and went to Khurasan. Akshah and Ozlagshahs will soon follow him. Since it is appropriate to note the activities of Jalaluddin separately, the activities of this great person will be discussed in detail in the following parts.

In Gurganj, the Kipchak warlords of the city - Ogul Hajib, Erbuqa Pahlavon and others declared the young Khumortegin, the nephew of Turkon Khatun, as "sultan". Khumortegin

was an incompetent, opinionated, cowardly person. Genghis Khan's sons Jochi, Chigatoy, Ogedey, famous Mongolian generals Tulun Cherbi, Ustun Noyon, Kazan Noyon and others arrived in Gurganj with their military forces. Since Khorezm was the first to be ruled by Jochi, he demanded that the city be handed over to the Mongols in peace. But in any case, the brave defenders of the city prepared for the defense and refused to hand over their city to the Mongols. The capital was surrounded by more than 100,000 Mongols. Catapults are set up to breach the city walls. The Mongols began to conquer the city with great force. Unfortunately, the new "sultan" could not lead the defense of the city. However, there was an army of 90 thousand people in the city.

The siege of Gurganj, which began in early 1221, lasted for almost seven months. The inhabitants of the city were not afraid of the weapons of the Mongols, slingshots and cannons, and started a valiant fight. Not afraid of spears and arrows, they begin to rebuild the damaged land of the city walls. A group of Urgan soldiers tried to attack the Mongols at a place called Bogi-Khurram, almost one farsah away from the city, and fought heroically.

However, according to Juvaini's writing, the Mongols, who were superior in terms of troops and weapons, together with the civilians and warriors of this land, killed more than 100,000 inhabitants. Faridun Ghuri, the chief of Sultan's officers, bravely defended the city walls and gates with his 500-strong military detachment. However, the cowardly and weak "sultan" Khumortegin opened the city gate and betrayed the Mongols in order to save his life. it happened. The invaders begin to invade the city.

According to historians Al-Nasawi and Juwaini, the residents of Gurganj defended every street and area with their whole heart. In the battle on the bridge, the townspeople managed to destroy more than 3000 Mongol soldiers.

Ahmad ibn Umar Abul Janab Najmiddin al-Kubro al-Khwaqi (1145-1221), a famous scholar, philosopher and scientist from Khorezm, the founder of the "Kubroviya" sect, also took an active part in the battles in the city. This 76-year-old great sheikh, who adopted the idea of "Homeland or honorable death" as his motto, rejected the Mongols' offers to surrender and participated in the internal defense of the city with his countless students, friends, and supporters. According to his call to battle, every inch of land will be heroically defended by the townspeople until a drop of their blood remains. Najmuddin Kubro fought heroically, before his death, he threw himself into the Mongol ship, killed him first, and then became a martyr himself.

The defense of the city was weakened, even between the sons of Genghis Khan, Jochi and Chigatai, there was a disagreement, and the occupation of the city was entrusted to another son - Ugedei. Countless blood was shed and the townspeople, feeling the futility of their last defense, had no choice but to surrender in order to save the lives of the survivors. The battle in the streets of the city continued for another seven days.

Cultural monuments, rich libraries with thousands of volumes became one with the earth. The pleas of the well-known cleric Olovuddin al-Hayat, who went to the townspeople to ask for safety, were also wasted. More than 100,000 artisans were separated from the city and sent to Mongolia. The inhabitants of the city were driven out to the steppe, children and women were taken. "Excess" captives were put to humiliating death.

According to Juvaini, there were 24 captured soldiers from the townspeople for every Mongolian soldier. Everything else was looted. After the capture of the city, its main part was

demolished and destroyed. The Mongols, who were not satisfied even with this satisfaction, destroyed the Amudarya dam and flooded the city. In this regard, al-Nasawi wrote that Gurganj "became a nest of vultures and a refuge for owls and crows."

Simultaneously with the siege of Gurganj, Genghis Khan turned his attention in the spring of 1221 to the rich cultural centers of Balkh, Herat, Ghazna, Kandahar, Nishapur, etc., located on major trade routes south of the Amudarya.

Genghis Khan personally led the Balkh campaign and conquered the city. He destroyed the inhabitants of Balkh. Some southern Khorezmshah viceroys, including Amin al-Mulk, treacherously defected to the Mongols. Nisa was the first city on the way of the Mongols in Khurasan.

The Mongols built 20 stone zamb arak (manjanik) and besieged the city continuously for 15 days. After capturing the city, they drove out its inhabitants and killed 70,000 inhabitants. In this regard, Al-Nasawi regretfully said, "They fed the beasts of the field and the birds of the sky with them. How much blood was spilled, how many women were raped, how many children were killed near the breasts of murdered mothers! And this was only one of the regions of Khorasan!" he wrote. Shahabeddin al-Hivaqi, one of the famous representatives of the Khorezmshah state, was also killed in Nisa. On the way, the Mongols put the representatives of the local population to the sword.

In February 1221, most of the inhabitants of Marv, a prominent city of Khorasan, fell on this day. The city of Marv was mercilessly looted several times. In the end, not a single person remained in the city. However, the city was famous in the Muslim world for its madrasahs, libraries, scholars, and was named "Marvi Jahon". During the fight against Jalalid, a number of fortresses and cities were occupied by fierce battles (Bamiyan, Ghazna, Kandahar, Gardiz, Valiyan, etc.). The last city occupied by the Mongols in the south was the city of Molton in northwestern India (1222).

It should be noted that within three years, the great Khorezmshah state was conquered by the Mongols. It should be noted here that Genghis Khan did not immediately implement the plan to conquer this country. If we look at the historical processes, it can be seen that in 1215, Genghis Khan declared to the sultan's ambassadors that he would recognize the power of Khorezmshah. In the next three years, as mentioned in the topic dedicated to the history of the Khorezmshahs, Genghis Khan will be aware of all the weak aspects of this kingdom. The removal of the local governors and officials from the state power by the sultan, the harsh relationship with the Caliphate of Baghdad, the fact that the huge (400,000) army of Khorezmshahs lost their skills in practice, internal political disputes, the sultan's conflict with the religious leaders, etc., came in very handy for the Mongols. Mongolian military tactics showed their superiority in the battles.

The sultan's instability, his overestimation of the power of the Mongols, his inability to analyze the situation properly and soundly, his doubts about the fate of the throne, the country, the kingdom, and others helped accelerate the destruction of the state. The Mongols used only death as the only way to subjugate the population.

In the sources, Urganch (Gurganj), which is called "the capital of the world's sultans" and "the cradle of the great children of mankind", Bukhara, the "bastion of Islam" in the East, Samarkand, the ancient homeland of Afro-Siab, "Qubbatul Islam" Balkh, famous for the

number of mosques (up to 1200), with its madrasas. the famous Marv, Nishapur and many famous cities were looted and destroyed.

Some cities that were hit hard by the Mongols, such as O'tror, Sig'noq, Borchilig'kent, etc., turned into deserts for a long time. The Arab historian Ibn al-Asir (1160-1244) who lived in this period wrote about the Mongol invasion: "They (that is, the Mongols) did not show mercy to anyone, on the contrary, they killed women, children, men, and killed unborn babies... This is a calamity. its waves spread in different directions, and its tragedy became general, and it spread over all the provinces as the wind drives the clouds in different directions. A nation came out from the borders of China and occupied provinces like Kashgar and Balasogun in Turkestan, Samarkand, Bukhara and other cities in Movarunnahr by destroying, slaughtering and looting. The Tatars did not leave any cities alive, they destroyed all the land on their way. They set fire to everything they did not like.

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